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1: Introduction

In this gravity theory I will present to you:

1: Introduction

2: Classical gravity formula, lever law... because they were used to build the theory.

3: System expansion

4: The formula (without expansion – the full version is at point 8)

5: Lever law built in

6: Asymmetry

7: Time delay & acceleration

8: Formula collection

9: Example calculation

10: Connection to modern physics

11: Possible applications

12: All formulas

13: Why orbits are not perfectly round

14: Comparison

15: Glossary

16: Conclusion

2:

Sir Isaac Newton came up with the theory of gravity in 1666, when supposedly an apple fell on his head.

This theory is one of the basic ingredients of my theory, which I will present to you later.

Albert Einstein came up with special relativity in 1905 and general relativity in 1915.

That is also important for part of the theory.

Asymmetry and the lever law are also part of the theory.

3: System expansion

My theory assumes that not only the mass of the sun attracts a planet, but also all the other objects around it, like planets, satellites, dust particles... If, for example, a planet leaves the system, the gravity of the sun changes. It becomes stronger because the total gravity is now less "distributed" and concentrated more on fewer objects. This applies not only to planets but also to satellites or dust particles.

4: The formula (without system expansion)

Let's start simple.

We know the gravity formula:

$$F = (G * M * m) / r^2$$

But if we now take away one planet, then the gravity on the remaining planets becomes slightly stronger. Because the "pull" is not spread over 10 anymore, but only over 9. And if we lose even more objects like dust or satellites, the gravity gets stronger and stronger.

This can be written like this:

$$F = (G * M * m) / r^2$$

With:

- F: normal gravity
- F_{eff} : new, increased gravity
- Delta M: lost mass
- M: total system mass
- alpha: strengthening factor

5: Lever law built in

The position of the missing object is important. If the planet disappears near the center, the gravity doesn't change much. But if the planet was far out, then the change is bigger. The farther away, the more effective the mass. Like with a lever.

This can be described with this formula:

$$F_{\text{eff}} = F * (1 + \alpha * ((\Delta m_i * r_i * \delta_i) / (M * R_{\text{max}})))$$

With:

- Δm_i : lost mass
- r_i : position of that mass
- R_{\max} : largest possible distance in the system
- rest: see above

6: Asymmetry

If the planet is gone, then the remaining planets are no longer evenly distributed around the sun. It gets "lopsided". That's called asymmetry. This has a small effect. But it becomes stronger with more missing mass. It's like putting 4 balls on a trampoline and then removing one; the surface bends differently now.

So:

We add a new factor to the formula: an asymmetry factor δ_i . It says how much the mass is no longer evenly distributed.

Formula:

$$F_{\text{eff}} = F * (1 + \alpha * ((\Delta m_i * r_i * \delta_i) / (M * R_{\max})))$$

7: Time delay / time acceleration

If the gravity gets stronger, then time flows more slowly (Einstein).

That means:

If the system loses mass, the gravity gets stronger → and time flows a bit slower than before. This is the same principle as time dilation from general relativity, but this time it is caused by mass loss in the system, not by speed or height.

8: Final formula

$$F_{\text{eff}} = (G * M * m) / r^2 * (1 + \beta * \Sigma((\Delta m_i * r_i * \delta_i) / (M * R_{\max}^2)))$$

This is the complete formula that includes mass loss, position, asymmetry, and time shift.

9: Example calculation

Let's say the sun has 1.989×10^{30} kg and the planet that disappears had 5.972×10^{24} kg (Earth). It was at a distance of 1.496×10^{11} meters (like Earth). And we say the asymmetry is 1 because the system becomes clearly unbalanced. Then the formula looks like this:

$$F_{\text{eff}} = (6.674 \times 10^{-11} \times 1.989 \times 10^{30} \times 1) / (1.496 \times 10^{11})^2 \\ * (1 + 1 * ((5.972 \times 10^{24} \times 1.496 \times 10^{11} \times 1) / (1.989 \times 10^{30} * (1.496 \times 10^{11})^2)))$$

Solution: $F_{\text{eff}} \approx 5.93 \times 10^{-3}$ N

10: Connection to modern physics

Einstein said that mass curves space-time. I say: the distribution of the mass is just as important. Because a system with many objects curves the space-time differently than a system with fewer objects. Especially if the objects are not evenly placed around the center. That is why my theory is not in contradiction with Einstein – it is more like a “system version” of it.

11: Possible applications

You could use the theory for many things: To calculate how strong the gravity was in the past or how it could change if many satellites crash or dust burns up. You could also calculate how much time difference there is. Or how a black hole would change if many planets fell into it. Because the position of the planets also matters. Maybe the theory also helps to understand how galaxy systems behave because even they lose mass over time. Or we could calculate where a gravitational imbalance could happen if too much space debris is on one side of a system.

12: All formulas

Here are all 6 formulas again together:

1: $F_{\text{eff}} = F * (1 + \alpha * (\Delta M / M))$ If mass disappears from the system (like a planet), the gravity becomes stronger.

2: $F_{\text{eff}} = F * (1 + \alpha * ((\Delta m_i * r_i) / (M * R_{\text{max}})))$ If the lost mass was far away, the gravity increases more – like with a lever.

3: $F_{\text{eff}} = F * (1 + \alpha * ((\Delta m_i * r_i * \delta_i) / (M * R_{\text{max}})))$ If the system becomes unbalanced (asymmetrical), gravity increases even more.

4: $F_{\text{eff}} = F * (1 + \alpha * ((\Delta m_i * r_i * \delta_i) / (M * R_{\text{max}}^2)))$ Like formula 3, but adds that time slows down when gravity changes.

5: $F_{\text{eff}} = F \cdot (1 + \alpha \cdot ((\Delta N / N) + (\Delta S_k / S_k) + (\Delta S / S)))$ This formula includes the loss of groups like planets (N), dust (Sk), or satellites (S).

6.(final): $F_{\text{eff}} = (G \cdot M \cdot m) / r^2 \cdot (1 + \beta \cdot \sum ((\Delta m_i \cdot r_i \cdot \delta_i) / (M \cdot R_{\text{max}}^2)))$ This is the full version with everything: Newton's gravity plus mass loss, position, asymmetry, and time delay.

$$1: F = \frac{G \cdot M \cdot m}{r^2}$$

$$2: F_{\text{eff}} = F \cdot (1 + \alpha \cdot \frac{\Delta M}{M})$$

$$3: F_{\text{eff}} = F \cdot (1 + \alpha \cdot (\frac{\Delta N}{N} + \frac{\Delta S_k}{S_k} + \frac{\Delta S}{S}))$$

$$4: F_{\text{eff}} = F \cdot (1 + \alpha \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\frac{\Delta m_i \cdot r_i}{M \cdot R_{\text{max}}}))$$

$$5: F_{\text{eff}} = F \cdot (1 + \alpha \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\frac{\Delta m_i \cdot r_i \cdot \delta_i}{M \cdot R_{\text{max}}}))$$

$$6: F_{\text{eff}} = \frac{G \cdot M \cdot m}{r^2} \cdot (1 + \beta \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\frac{\Delta m_i \cdot r_i \cdot \delta_i}{M \cdot R_{\text{max}}^2}))$$

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13: Why orbits are not perfectly round

In the past, people thought: Planets move in perfect circles. Later it turned out: they don't. They move in ellipses. Some say it's because of speed and angles. Others say: because of the influence of other planets. But my theory adds something new: If planets are not evenly placed, then gravity pulls more from one side. That changes the orbit even a little bit. Like with a trampoline: If one ball is removed from one side, the shape changes. That's why orbits are not perfectly round.

14: Comparison

We all know atoms. And we know that if an atom loses an electron, then the attraction of the nucleus gets stronger because there's less repulsion. It's the same in my theory: If the system loses one "orbiting object" (planet, satellite...), then the center (like the sun) attracts more strongly – because fewer objects are left.

So: Less mass = more attraction = slower time. This is exactly like in atoms.

15: Glossary

Term / Symbol	Meaning
G	Gravitational constant (6.674×10^{-11})
M	Central mass (e.g. the sun)
m	Object mass (e.g. a planet)
r	Distance between the two masses
Delta M	Lost mass in the system
Delta m _i	Lost individual mass
r _i	Position of that mass
delta _i	Asymmetry factor
R _{max}	Maximum system radius
alpha	Strengthening factor
beta	Bending factor of space-time

S	Satellites
S _k	Dust particles
N	Planets
F	Classical gravitational force
F _{eff}	New, effective gravity (with system effect)

16: Conclusion

The theory is just a theory. But it shows that maybe gravity is not just about two bodies. Maybe it is a full system. Where every object matters. Even dust. Even satellites. It also shows: Mass is not the only thing that matters but also where it is and how much of it is missing. This is my own theory. And I hope someone will test it. Thank you for reading.

— Kuzey Çetindere